

Master of Public Administration (MPA) Programme

Madhesh University

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Master of Public Administration (MPA) Programme

Introduction of the Programme

Madhesh University (MU) is committed to offering various streams of academic programmes of different levels preparing students capable and competent to contribute in enhancing the socio-economic advancement of society and nation. In this perspective, MU is designed Master in Public Administration program to provide a developmental framework for those interested in leadership and management in public service. This programme intends to prepare current and future leaders in public and nonprofit sectors through high-quality education that fosters collaboration, inclusivity, and adaptability. It provides students with a comprehensive core curriculum in public affairs as well as a broad set of electives to prepare them to solve difficult administrative and policy problems in local, state, national, and global communities.

The course has been designed that crosses all the traditional boundaries, students graduate with the very latest analytic frameworks that will serve them in the numerous positions within organizations all over the world. The programme emphasizes public service values while facilitating intellectual and professional development through learning experiences that integrate theory with practice. We provide a culture that promotes integrity and diversity and advances governance while preparing students to reach standards of excellence in public service. In essence, the programme aims to provide a high level of competence in public policy, governance, and administration;

Programme Goals

All graduates of the programme will be able to:

- 1) Address the administrative using knowledge of the practice of public administration
- 2) Analyze and evaluate the ethical implications of decisions made by public administrators in the public interest
- 3) Analyze public policy, public programs, and/or public services using critical thinking skills
- 4) Demonstrate the decision-making skills necessary for leadership in the public sector
- 5) Develop enhanced skills in ethical leadership, communication, teamwork, and self-management
- 6) Apply rigorous analytical skills for organisational learning, including evidence-based decision-making in response to the complexities and challenges of public administration and governance

Curriculum Structure

The MPA curriculum is built around three integrated components:

- 1) A professional 'core' of knowledge broadly recognised as essential to the institutional role of public sector managers.

- 2) A specialized course in major public sector areas providing emerging concepts and techniques relevant to contemporary professional practice.
- 3) A research based experiential learning capstone that allows students to select research area to suit the interests and professional development needs.

Eligibility for Admission

Candidates who have completed a bachelor's degree in any disciplines recognized by Government of Nepal are eligible for MPA study. The prospective students should pass an entrance test to get admission in MPA. Successful candidates will be admitted based on merit.

Admission Test

Admission to the programme is based on an assessment of an applicant's ability and potential to meet the demands of a rigorous graduate programme. The University conducts an entrance test for the enrollment of students at MPA level.

Evaluation, Grading, Attendance, and Scholarship

Evaluation and Grading

Total marks obtained in internal and end- semester exams shall be graded on absolute or relative bases. The performance of a student shall be evaluated on a four-point scale ranging from 0 to 4.

Grade Point Average

A student must secure a minimum Grade Point Average (GPA) of 2.7 or Grade B minus (B-) in each course as mentioned below.

In each course, students will be evaluated on a 4-point scale as follows:

Grade	A	A-	B+	B	B-	C+	C	F
Grade Point	4.0	3.7	3.3	3.0	2.7	2.3	2.0	0

The grades indicate the quality of a student's performance as follows:

- A = Outstanding,
- A- = Excellent,
- B+ = Very Good,
- B = Good
- B- = Fair,
- C+ = Fair,
- C = Fair,
- F = Failure

Make-up/Retake Examination

Students will have a chance to appear in make-up or retake examination who failed in the first, second and third semesters conducted by MU. Make-up or retake exams will be conducted as per the provisions of MU.

Duration of the Study

The duration for the completion of the requirements for the MPA program are as follows:

- Normal duration of 24 months (4 Semesters)
- Maximum duration for the completion of course work and/or thesis writing should be within 60 months, i.e. 5 years.

Attendance

Students have to maintain minimum 80 percent attendance and those who could not fulfill are not allowed to appear in the semester-end examination and regarded as "not qualified." However, in case of serious illness, the students with 50 percent attendance will be given a chance to appear in the end semester exam. In this case, students have to submit an authorized medical certificate. The final decision will be with the faculty head.

Scholarship

There is a provision of waiver of the tuition fees as decided by the office of the dean. Such tuition fee waiver will be made on the basis of merit and socio-economic condition of the student.

Teaching Pedagogy

Primarily, interactive classes will be adopted as main teaching pedagogy where active student participation and collaborative learning will be persuaded followed by class lectures, problem-solving exercises and case analysis will be conducted. For developing research competency peer review presentation, field work, mini research, capstone study and a research work will be undertaken.

Course Structure for a 2-Year MPA

First Year

Semester 1

Course Code	Course Title	Credits
MPA511	Public Affairs Management	3
MPA 513	Political economy and Public Policy Making	3
MPA 517	Human Resource Management and Organization Behaviour in Public Sector	3
MPA 516	Research Methods in Public Administration	3
MPA 515	Public Finance and Public Fiscal Management	3
MPA 510	Practice of Governance	3

Total Credits for Semester 1: 18

Semester 2

Course Code	Course Title	Credits
MPA 512	Administrative Law, Ethics and Governance	3
MPA 514	Development Administration	3
MPA 521	Public Service Delivery	3
MPA 516	Federalism and Intergovernmental Management	3
PA 520	Statistics for Public Administration	3

Total Credits for Semester 2: 15

Second Year

Semester 3

Course Code	Course Title	Credits
MPA 518	Local Governance and Administration	3
MPA 522	Information Technology in Public Administration	3
MPA 523	International Administration	3
Specialization	2 courses	6

Total Credits for Semester 3: 15

Semester 4

Thesis for 9 credits extended from third semester research project

MPA 524 PUBLIC Policy Analysis and Evaluation (3 credits)

Specialization Courses (Choose any two from the following)

General Administration

- Public policy governance
- Multilevel Governance
- Public Finance Governance
- Development and Governance

Development and Governance

- DA 621 Rural Development (3 credits)
- DA 622 Urban Development (3 credits)
- DA 623 Development planning (3 credits)

Project Administration

- PM 605 Project Management (3 credits)
- PM 625 Project Administration (3 credits)
- PM 635 Sustainable Humanitarian Action

Human Resource Development

- HRD 650 Human Resource Management (3 credits)
- HRD 660 Labor Policy and Administration (3 credits)

- HRD 670 Occupational Safety and Health Management (3 Credits)

Public Finance

- PFN 680 Financial Planning and Budgeting (3 credits)
- PFN 685 Financial Management for Sustainable Humanitarian Action
- PFN 687 Finance for Project Management

Law and Order Administration

- LOA 690 Law Enforcement Management (3 credits)
- LOA 700 Public Procurement Advanced
- LOA 705 Professional Practice

Thesis Option

- Thesis Writing (6 credits)

Total Credits for Semester 4: Varies based on course selection

Summary of Program Components

- 1) **Core Courses:** Fundamental knowledge essential for public administration.
- 2) **Elective/Specialization Courses:** Allows students to tailor their education to specific interests within public administration.
- 3) **Thesis Writing:** Optional but recommended for those looking engaging in research.

The total credit hours required for the MPA program typically range between **66 to 72 credits**, depending on the batch's specific requirements and elective choices. The Dean office can extend specific courses as per need assessment to ensure upgraded syllabus.

Course Details

MPA511: Public Affairs Management

Credit hours :3

Lecture hours : 48

Course Description

The course captures the thematic approach to the evolution and development of public sector management, and encourages students to consider their relevance to their own context. The course gives particular emphasis to issues of functioning of government and politics and Public Administration interface.

Course Objectives

Following expectations have been considered after the successful completion of this course. Students will have the knowledge and skills to:

- 1) Understand the key concepts, ideas, theories and terminology associated with public administration and public sector management;
- 2) Understand the main issues in key theoretical debates in public administration and public sector management.
- 3) Apply relevant concepts and theories;
- 4) Demonstrate improved capacity for critical analysis as well as for clear and effective communication.

Course Contents

- 1) Public Affairs : Scope of Public affairs, Public Affairs defined, Context of Public Affairs, Public Affairs: knowledge , skills and Behaviour (6 LHs)
- 2) Introduction to Public Administration: Concept, Scope, Roles and Importance , Public Administration and Private Administration , Paradigm shifts in public Administration including New Public Management, New Public Service and New Public Governance (12 LHs)
- 3) Management and Organization Theory : Organization Theory: Classical approaches (scientific management, organization and management; and bureaucratic theory), neo-classical approach (human relations and behavioral approach, structural organization theory) and system theory (10LHs)
- 4) Machinery of Government: Working of Bureaucracy, Decision making cycle and Process , Coordination (10 LHs)
- 5) Politics and Public Administration : Democracy and Public Administration, Politics-Bureaucracy Interface (6 LHs)
- 6) Building Trust in Government (4 LHs)

References

- Bovaird, T., & Löffler, E. (2003). *Public management and governance*. Routledge.
- Cheema, G. S., & Popovski, V. (Eds.). (2010). *Building trust in government: Innovations in governance reform in Asia*. UNU Press.
- Fox, R. C. (2007). *Democracy and public administration*. Sharpe.
- Frederickson, H. G., Smith, K. B., Larimer, C., & Licari, M. J. (2012). *Public administration primer* (2nd ed.). Westview Press.
- Henry, N. (n.d.). *Public administration and public affairs*. Prentice Hall.
- Hughes, O. (2012). *Public management & administration* (4th ed.). Palgrave Macmillan.
- Osborne, S. (Ed.). (2010). *The new public governance*. Routledge.
- Peters, B. G., & Thynne, I. (Eds.). (2022). *The Oxford encyclopedia of public administration* (2 vols.). Oxford University Press.
- van der Wal, Z. (2017). *The 21st century public manager*. Bloomsbury Academic.

MPA 513: Political economy and Public Policy Making

Course Description

The Political Economy and Public Policy emphasizes the results of the interactions between the economic and political systems in terms of policy formulation, policy implementation and policy evaluation. This course offers an excellent preparation for those interested in careers and those who aspire to contribute in the public policy arena.

Course Objectives

By the end of the course students should be able to:

- Understand the basis of public policy analysis and evidence-based public policy.
- Understand the public policy-making cycle
- Able to analyze social issues from a policy perspective
- Understand the different analytical methods used to perform policy evaluation.

Course Content

- 1) **Introduction to Public Policy and Political Economy:** Concept , historical evolution of Political economy thought, and Theories of State-Market Relations (Classical Liberalism, Keynesianism, Neoliberalism, Institutionalism, Marxism), Political institutions and Public Policy (Democracies, Autocracies, Monarchism, Theocracies) (6 LHs)
- 2) **Public policy:** Concept, Categories of Public Policy, Nature and scope of public policy Typology of public policy, Scope of public policy (6 LHs)
- 3) **Models of Policy Analysis:** Policy as Political activity, Political Systems Theory, Group Theory, Elite Theory, Institutionalism, Rational Choice Theory, Public choice Theory, Game Theory (10 LHs)
- 4) **The Policy making Process:** Problem identification and agenda setting, Formulating Policy, Policy Legitimation, Policy Implementation-Bureaucracy (8 LHs)
- 5) **Public Policy Decision Making:** Rational decision making, Disjointed instrumentalism, Mixed scanning, Public opinion model , Concept of bounded rationality (LHs 10)
- 6) **Policy Evaluation:** Assessing the impact of Public Policy, Programme evaluation , Experimental policy research (8 LHs)

References

- Anderson, J. E. (2003). *Public policymaking: An introduction*. Boston, MA: Houghton Mifflin.
- Cochran, C. L., & Malone, E. F. (2007). *Public policy: Perspectives and choices*. New Delhi, India: Viva Books Pvt. Ltd.
- Dye, T. R. (2013). *Understanding public policy* (15th ed.). Boston, MA: Pearson.
- Hill, M., & Hupe, P. (2006). *Implementing public policy: Governance in theory and practice*. New Delhi, India: Sage Publications.
- Howlett, M., & Ramesh, M. (2003). *Studying public policy: Policy cycles and policy subsystems*. New York, NY: Oxford University Press.

MPA 517: Human Resource Management and Organization Behaviour in Public Sector

Credit Hours: 3

Lecture Hours: 48

Course Description

This course provides a compressive, comprehensive and broad outlook for navigating the complexities of organizational behavior and human resource management in public sector. It highlights the ever-changing landscape and challenges in human sphere driven by technological advancements and evolving employee expectations and to manage the change in organization effectively.

Course Objectives

After the completion of the course, students will be able to:

- 1) Manage of human resources in respective organisations;
- 2) Explain the importance and steps of human resource planning;
- 3) Understand managing diverse workforce
- 4) Understand theories, models, and methods for organizational behaviours
- 5) Critically discuss human behaviours in the workplace from a relevant theoretical standpoint

Human Resource Management in Public Sector

- 1 Introduction to HR Management in the Public Sector (LHs 4)
- 2 Strategic Human Resource Management and Planning, E -HRM (LHs 8)
- 3 Career and Competency Development, Methods and Functions of Human Resource management : Job Analysis and Job Design, Recruitment and Selection, Compensation and Benefits, Training and Development (LHs 4)
- 4 Empolyee Coaching and Counseling Performance Management (LHs 4)
- 5 Managing a Diverse Workforce (LHs 4)

Organizational Behaviour in the Public Sector

- 1) Introduction to Organizational Behavior in the Public Sector (LHs 4)
- 2) Individual Behavior in Organizations (Personality and Individual Differences Perception, Motivation, Learning) (LHs 6)
- 3) Group and Team Dynamics (Formation and Development of Groups, Team Building and Effectiveness, Communication in Teams, Conflict Management, Leadership) (LHs 6)
- 4) Cross Cultural HRM, Organizational Culture and Climate (Understanding Organizational Culture, Impact of Organizational Culture on Behavior, Creating a Positive Organizational Climate, Managing Cultural Diversity) (LHs 4)

- 5) Organization Change – a) Change in Organizations, b) Nature of the change process, c) Types of change, d) Impact of change, e) Managing resistance to change, f) Organizational Development interventions (LHs 4)

References

- Daly, J. (2010). *Human resource management in the public sector*. Routledge.
- Greenberg, J., & Baron, R. A. (2008). *Behaviour in organizations*. New Delhi, India: PHI Learning Private Ltd.
- Griffin, R., Phillips, J., Gully, S., Creed, A., Gribble, L., & Watson, M. (2024). *Organisational behaviour: Engaging people and organisations*. Cengage Learning Australia.
- Nankervis, A., Compton, A., Baird, M., & Coffey, J. (2011). *Human resource management: Strategy and practice* (7th ed.). Cengage Learning Australia.
- Niruba Rani, J., Mishra, A. K., & Satheesh, A. (2024). *Strategic human resource management*. Priyam Publication. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14581988>
- Pynes, J. E. (2009). *Human resources management for public and nonprofit organizations: A strategic approach* (3rd ed.). Jossey-Bass.
- Robbins, S. P., & Judge, T. A. (2011). *Organizational behaviour* (14th ed.). Pearson.

MPA 516: Research Methods in Public Administration

Credit Hours: 3

Lecture Hours: 48

Course Description

This course intends to equip students to build their research competencies having gained knowledge on the major elements of research Process. The course includes theoretical knowledge on Research Problem, Research Design, Sampling Techniques, Research Proposal, Data Collection, Data Analysis, and Research Report. It equips students with the knowledge and skills to conduct rigorous and ethical research.

COURSE OBJECTIVES

- Enabling the participants to understand various Research Methodologies that can be directly used to conduct research
- Enabling participants to learn about qualitative, quantitative, hybrid / mixed research.
- Preparing Research Papers and Reports

Course Contents

Unit 1: Basic concept of research and Public Administration Research (6 LHS)

Nature of social and behavioral science

- Objectives and Approaches of research
- Types of research like Qualitative, Quantitative, Mixed research

Unit 2 Research Process (6LHS)

- Scientific Methods
- Research problem and hypothesis
- Variables and their relationships
- Measurement and scaling; reliability and validity of measuring instruments
- Sources of data (primary and secondary)
- Ethics and value judgment in social research

Unit 3: Literature Review (LHs 4)

- Concept, process and purpose of literature review
- Citation systems: APA and others

Unit 4: Sampling and Data Collection Methods (LHs 6)

- **Sampling:** basic concept
- Probability and non-probability sampling methods and their techniques
- **Survey method:** questionnaire construction and structured interview
- Unstructured interviews, observation, content analysis, and document study
- **Participatory approaches:** RRA and PRA

Unit 5 Research Design I (LHs 8)

- **Quantitative Research:** Descriptive Research: Survey methods. Causal research – Experimentation research labs v/s field experiments

Unit 6 Research Design II (LHs 8)

- **Qualitative Research:** Observation, Focus Group, Depth Interview, Projective Techniques

Unit 7: Data Analysis and Report Writing (LH 6)

- **Quantitative Data Analysis:** Descriptive Analysis, Bi-variate and Multivariate Analysis.
- Qualitative field work. Qualitative Data Analysis
- Use of computer software for data analysis
- Data presentation, interpretation and generalization

Unit 8 Research Proposal Writing This course (4 LHs)

- Structure and process of writing a thesis

References

- Creswell, J. W. (2009). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (3rd ed.). New Delhi, India: Sage Publications Pvt. Ltd.
- Kerlinger, F. N. (2000). *Foundations of behavioural research* (4th ed.). New Delhi, India: Surjeet Publications.
- Kothari, C. R. (2010). *Research methodology: Methods and techniques* (2nd rev. ed.). New Delhi, India: New Age International Pvt. Ltd.
- Pant, P. R. (2016). *Social science research and thesis writing*. Kathmandu, Nepal: Buddha Academic Publishers.
- Rassel, G., Leland, S., Mohr, Z., & O’Sullivan-Baskota, E. (2020). *Research methods for public administrators* (6th ed.). Routledge.
- Sekaran, U. (2016). *Research methods for business: A skill-building approach* (7th ed.). Wiley India.
- van Thiel, S. (2021). *Research methods in public administration and public management*. London: Routledge.

MPA 515: Public Finance and Public Fiscal Management

The course acquaints students with the purposes, characteristics, processes, and operations of financial management systems and develops their capabilities to analyze financial operations, coordinate such operations with relevant public policies and programs, and effectively manage the financial resources of public entities.

Course Objectives

The course intends to fulfill following objectives:

- Students will have a comprehensive understanding of the key principles, concepts, and practices of public financial management.
- Students equip with the knowledge and skills necessary to effectively manage public resources.
- Understand the budget preparation process and explore alternative budgeting approaches.
- Students will be capable to. assess and design revenue-generation strategies.
- Students will understand the dynamics of intergovernmental fiscal relationship.

Course Content

1) Fundamental Principles of Public Finance (LHs 6)

Meaning, Concept, Scope and Importance of Public Finance , Comparison between public finance and private finance, Public Finance Cycle, Principles of Public Finance (Principle of Maximum Social Advantage, Marginal Social sacrifice, marginal Social Benefit

2) Budgeting: (LHs 10)

The Logic of the Budget Process. Concept of government budgeting; Theories of budgeting, Classical and modern concepts of budgeting, Types /classification of budgeting, Process of government budgeting in Nepal and medium-term expenditure framework (MTEF), Fiscal Risk, Fiscal Responsibility and Fiscal Rules

3) Revenue Administration (LHs 8)

Concept of public revenue, cannons of taxation, principles of taxation: benefit principle and ability to pay principle, Characteristics of effective tax system, Tax policy design considerations and tax administration

4) Public Expenditure Management (LHs 6)

Concept, structure and principles of public expenditure, pattern of public expenditure, public expenditure financial accountability (PEFA), Budget Execution: Compliance, Adaptability, Efficiency

5) Debt Management . (LHs 6)

Concept and need of public debt, Sources and structure of public debt, Burden of public debt, Principles of debt management, Debt management strategies, Public debt Risk Management, Debt Trap.

- 6) Digital transformation of tax and customs administrations. (LHs 6)
- 7) Intergovernmental Fiscal Relations: Diversity and Coordination. (LHs 6)

References:

Bhatia, H. L. (2010). *Public finance*. New Delhi, India: Vikas Publishing House Pvt. Ltd.

Junquera-Varela, R. F., & Lucas-Mas, C. Ó. (2024). *Revenue administration handbook*. Washington, DC: World Bank.

Mikesell, J. L. (2025). *Fiscal administration* (11th ed.). Cengage Learning.

Schiavo-Campo, S. (2017). *Government budgeting and expenditure management: Principles and international practice*. Routledge.

Singh, C. (2016). *Public debt management*. Singapore: Springer.

Singh, S. K. (2010). *Public finance: In theory and practice*. New Delhi, India: S. Chand & Company Pvt. Ltd.

The course objective for MPA 512 Practice of Governance is to enable students to understand and analyze governance practices through direct field observation, active discussion, presentations, and interactive sessions, thereby developing their skills to critically assess governance processes and effectively prepare concise reports based on their experiential learning. The evaluation will be done by the faculty continuously as per class performance only.

Course Objectives:

The course intends to fulfill following objectives.

- Equip students to understand governance practices through direct field observation.
- Develop analytical skills by engaging in active discussions on governance issues.
- Improve communication skills through presentations and interactive sessions.
- Foster critical assessment of governance processes based on real-world experiences.
- Train students to prepare clear and concise reports reflecting their observations and learning.
- Encourage continuous learning and performance evaluation through regular faculty assessment during class activities.

Course Content

- 1) Structure of Peer Review Paper (LHs 4)
Meaning, Concept, Scope and Importance of Peer Review, Structure of the paper
- 2) Understanding by Reading Peer Review (LHs 10)
The Students should read a peer reviewed paper and express their understanding related public administration issues
- 3) Review of Different papers in group with specific themes of administration and Table Preparation on students understanding (LHs 8)
- 4) Public Speaking, Naming Phonetics (LHs 6)
- 5) Personality Development Exercise (LHs 6)
- 6) Expression of students through reading and discussion (LHs 6)
- 7) Reporting by students and presentation as seminar (LHs 6)

References

- Rassel, G., Leland, S., Mohr, Z., & O'Sullivan, E. (2020). *Research methods for public administrators* (7th ed.). Routledge.
- ThielS van. (2021). *Research Methods in Public Administration and Public Management*. Routledge.
- Mishra, A. K. (2022). *A reference book on comparative assessment from the Eastern approach*. Intellectual's Book Palace. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7113124>
- Mishra, A. K., Nirubarani, J., Radha, P., Priyadharshini, R., & Mishra, S. (2025). *Artificial and emotional intelligence for employee*. Intellectuals' Book Palace. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14810072>